

OpenBiodiv

Open Biodiversity Knowledge Management System

A joint project of

One Effort May Have Many Valuable Outputs

Pensoft and Plazi join forces to provide an **enhanced publishing, text and data mining, archiving and indexing infrastructure** to extract **interoperable data** from literature **in an unprecedented way!**

Consultancy and support
in journal conversion to
XML & RDF

Production,
publishing, indexing
and archiving

Text and data
mining from legacy
content

